

Numerical investigation of the effects of compressibility on the flutter of a three-dimensional, cantilevered plate in an inviscid, subsonic, open flow

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Abstract

In this work we carry out a numerical study of the influence of the upstream Mach number on the flutter of a three-dimensional, cantilevered, flexible plate subject to a subsonic, inviscid, open flow. We have assumed a linear elastic model for the plate and that the fluid flow is governed by the linearized potential theory. The fluid equations are solved by means of a doublet point method to obtain the generalized aerodynamic forces as a function of the plate displacements. Then, these generalized forces are coupled to the equation of motion of the plate, which is discretized with a spectral Galerkin method, and an eigenvalue analysis is performed to find the flutter point. The obtained results are in good agreement with those of related theoretical and experimental studies found in the literature.

Keywords: airfoil-fluid interaction, compressible subsonic flow, cantilevered plate, flutter, linearized potential flow, unsteady aerodynamics

1. Introduction

The flutter of a cantilevered plate has received great attention in the field of aeroelasticity –see, for example, the references by Dowell [1] and Païdoussis [2]– as it provides an insight to many other fluid-structure interaction problems such as aircraft wing flutter [3], train panel flutter [4], energy harvesting [5, 6], human snoring [7] and paper web instability [8]. However, as we briefly review next, the major part of the results found in the literature are restricted to incompressible flows, whereas the effect of the compressibility –that may not be negligible, e.g., in aircraft wing flutter or train panel flutter– seems to have received little attention, especially in the case of three-dimensional panels.

Such a lack of attention may be caused by the fact that it is more difficult to obtain a direct relationship between the aerodynamic loads over the plate and its motion when the flow is compressible. In effect, the numerical analysis of the flutter phenomenon is usually approached by coupling the equation of motion of the plate to an appropriate aerodynamic model that provides the unsteady fluid pressures over the plate given its motion. In the incompressible case, some of these aerodynamic models are based on theoretical relations [9, 10] obtained by Theodorsen [11] and Küssner and Schwartz [12] for unsteady, linearized, incompressible flows, as is done, e.g., in the works of Kornecki [13, 14], Huang [7], Guo and Païdoussis [15], Eloy et al. [16, 17], Li et al. [18–20] and Drazumeric et al. [21]. However, this procedure cannot be extended to linearized, compressible flows because, in this case, the relation between aerodynamic forces and the airfoil motion is governed by the more complicated Possio’s equation, for which no analytical solution is known, but only an approximated one [22].

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An alternative procedure to obtain the aerodynamic pressures over the plate given its motion is to directly solve the Navier-Stokes equations, as has been done by Watanabe et al. [8], Balint and Lucey [23], Khalili et al. [24] and Cisonni et al. [25]. Some of these authors [8, 24] have also considered compressibility effects for the case of very small Mach numbers, but their methods have proved to be too expensive compared to those based on potential flow theory [8]. Therefore, in order to deal with compressibility effects at higher Mach numbers, some investigators have tried an approach based on the direct discretization in space and in time of the linearized, compressible, potential flow equations. This is done, for example, in the papers of Li and Yang –who implemented a differential quadrature method restricted to panels wetted by one side–, Huang and Zhang [26] –who formulated a Chebyshev pseudospectral method– and of Colera and Pérez-Saborid [27, 28] –who employed finite differences. Apparently, only the latter authors effectively applied their method to compressible flows and panels wetted by the two sides –Huang and Zhang only considered the case of zero Mach number–, although their results were restricted to the two-dimensional case.

Some other aerodynamic models are based on panel methods, as happens in the works of Yamaguchi et al. [29], Tanida [30], D. Tang et al. [3], Argentina and Mahadevan [31], L. Tang and Païdoussis [32, 33], L. Tang et al. [5, 34], Gibbs et al. [35], Zhao et al. [36], Howell and Lucey [37, 38], Alben [39], Michelin and Llewellyn Smith [40] and Colera and Pérez-Saborid [41]. As far as we know, only [30] and [41] apply this methodology for the case of compressible flows, and their results are restricted again to the two-dimensional case.

In this work, we extend the investigations of [28, 30, 41] by performing a parametric study of the flutter speed and the flutter frequency of a **plate cantilevered at the leading edge in a three-dimensional, inviscid, compressible, subsonic flow** as a function of its mechanical properties and the upstream Mach number. For that purpose, we have developed a numerical scheme based on discretizing the plate equations through a spectral Galerkin formulation and on solving the (linear) aerodynamic equations with a slight modification of the Ueda-Dowell doublet point method [42]. **It must be pointed that the methodology and the parametric study presented here are clearly inspired on those of a previous work [28], with the difference that here we employ a three-dimensional formulation instead of a two-dimensional one. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first computational investigation of the effects of compressibility on the flutter of a plate cantilevered at the leading edge in a three dimensional, inviscid, subsonic flow carried out in the literature.**

The paper is structured as follows. First, the equations of motion of the plate are introduced in section 2. Then, in section 3, the Ueda-Dowell doublet point method is briefly reviewed, and two modifications are proposed to reduce its computational cost in the case of rectangular plates. The computation of the flutter curves of the plate is explained in section 4, whereas the results are discussed in section 5. Finally, some conclusions and future developments are pointed out in section 6.

2. Dynamic model of the plate

Consider a cantilevered, flexible, flat plate of dimensions $L \times H$ lying in the $x - y$ plane, as depicted in Fig. 1, and let an incident flow —of density ρ_∞ , speed U_∞ and Mach number M_∞ — come in the x direction.

Figure 1: Scheme of a cantilevered flexible plate subject to an incident flow.

75 Since we are interested in computing just the flutter point of the plate, and not its post-critical (non-
76 linear) behavior, the linear, elastic, Kirchhoff's model can be used. In that case, the displacements of the
77 mean line of the plate, $z_p(t, x)$, are governed by the equation [17, 43]

$$\sigma \frac{\partial^2 z_p}{\partial t^2} + D \nabla^4 z_p = \Delta p, \quad (1)$$

78 where σ is the surface mass density, Δp is the pressure difference between the lower and the upper parts of
79 the plate, and D is the flexural rigidity. The latter is given by $D = Eh_p^3/12/(1 - \nu^2)$, where E , h_p and ν
80 are Young's modulus, the plate thickness and Poisson's coefficient, respectively.

81 The displacements of the mean line are expressed as follows. First, we generate a rectangular grid of
82 $N_x^m \times N_y^m$ Chebyshev nodes, i.e., the (i, j) point of the grid is defined by the coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} x_i^m &= \frac{L}{2} - \frac{L}{2} \cos\left(\pi \frac{i-1}{N_x^m - 1}\right), & i &= 1, \dots, N_x^m, \\ y_j^m &= -\frac{H}{2} \cos\left(\pi \frac{j-1}{N_y^m - 1}\right), & j &= 1, \dots, N_y^m. \end{aligned}$$

83 For brevity, the latter grid is to be referred with the name of *mechanical grid* and with the superindex
84 m along this work, and sometimes the grid point (i, j) will be denoted by a single index $I(i, j)$ defined as
85 $I = i + (j - 1)N_x^m$. Then, z_p is described in terms of a two-dimensional interpolation as

$$z_p(x, y) = \sum_{I=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \psi_I^m(x, y) q_I, \quad (2)$$

86 with $\psi_I^m(x, y)$ the two-dimensional Lagrange polynomial associated to the node I and $q_I := z_p(x_I^m, y_I^m)$.

87 Note that we have to impose yet the restrictions

$$z_p = 0, \quad \frac{\partial z_p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, \quad (3)$$

88 in order to adequately represent the motion of a cantilevered plate. Since, for a fixed value of x , both z_p
89 and $\partial z_p / \partial x$ are polynomials of degree $N_y^m - 1$ in y , it is sufficient to impose $z_p = 0$ and $\partial z_p / \partial x = 0$ at the
90 edge nodes to ensure (3) is verified. That is,

$$q_I = 0, \quad \sum_{J=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \frac{\partial \psi_J^m}{\partial x}(x_I^m, y_I^m) q_J = 0, \quad I = 1, 1 + N_x^m, \dots, 1 + (N_y^m - 1)N_x^m, \quad (4)$$

91 or, equivalently,

$$\mathbf{R} \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (5)$$

92 with \mathbf{R} a $2N_y^m \times N_x^m N_y^m$ restriction matrix whose elements can be readily deduced from (4) and $[\mathbf{q}]_I := q_I$.

93 Now, we multiply equation (1) by a virtual displacement δz_p -compatible with restrictions (3)- and
94 operate to obtain the virtual work principle [43]

$$\int_S \delta z_p \sigma \frac{\partial^2 z_p}{\partial t^2} dS + \int_S (\mathbf{L} \delta z_p)^T \mathbf{D} (\mathbf{L} \delta z_p) dS = \int_S \delta z_p \Delta p dS,$$

95 with S the plate domain,

$$\mathbf{L} = \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}, \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}, \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \right]^T, \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1 - \nu}{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

96 Note that no virtual work is performed at the boundary since, in the free edges, there are no forces nor
 97 moments, whereas in the clamped edge there are no virtual displacements nor virtual rotations. Expanding
 98 δz_p and z_p in terms of (2), we obtain

$$\sum_{I=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \delta q_I \sum_{J=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \left[\int_S \sigma \psi_I^m \psi_J^m \frac{\partial^2 q_J}{\partial t^2} dS + \int_S (\mathbf{L}\psi_I^m)^T \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{L}\psi_J^m) q_J dS - \int_S \Delta p \psi_J^m q_J dS \right] = 0. \quad (6)$$

99 The restrictions between the δq_I 's are imposed via Lagrange multipliers. That is, since

$$\sum_{I=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} [\mathbf{R}]_{K,I} \delta q_I = 0, \quad K = 1, \dots, 2N_y^m,$$

100 we can rewrite equation (6) as

$$\sum_{I=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \delta q_I \left\{ \sum_{J=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \left[\int_S \sigma \psi_I^m \psi_J^m \frac{\partial^2 q_J}{\partial t^2} dS + \int_S (\mathbf{L}\psi_I^m)^T \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{L}\psi_J^m) q_J dS - \int_S \Delta p \psi_J^m q_J dS \right] + \sum_{K=1}^{K=2N_y^m} [\mathbf{R}]_{K,I} \lambda_K \right\} = 0,$$

101 for any λ_K 's. Then, we choose the λ_K 's so that [44]

$$\sum_{J=1}^{N_x^m N_y^m} \left[\int_S \sigma \psi_I^m \psi_J^m \frac{\partial^2 q_J}{\partial t^2} dS + \int_S (\mathbf{L}\psi_I^m)^T \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{L}\psi_J^m) q_J dS - \int_S \Delta p \psi_J^m q_J dS \right] + \sum_{K=1}^{K=2N_y^m} [\mathbf{R}]_{K,I} \lambda_K = 0, \quad \forall I. \quad (7)$$

102 Finally, since the plate motion is harmonic at the flutter point, we seek solutions of the form

$$\begin{aligned} q_i(t) &= \operatorname{Re} [\tilde{q}_i \exp(j\omega t)], \\ \Delta p(t, x) &= \operatorname{Re} [\Delta \tilde{p}(x) \exp(j\omega t)], \\ \lambda_K(t) &= \operatorname{Re} [\tilde{\lambda}_K \exp(j\omega t)], \end{aligned}$$

103 where j is the complex unit and ω is the frequency of the motion. In this case, equations (5) and (7) lead
 104 to the saddle point problem

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{R}^T \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

105 with

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{M}]_{IJ} &= \int_S \sigma \psi_I^m \psi_J^m dS, \quad [\mathbf{K}]_{IJ} = \int_S (\mathbf{L}\psi_I^m)^T \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{L}\psi_J^m) dS, \quad [\tilde{\mathbf{q}}]_J = \tilde{q}_J, \quad [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}]_K = \tilde{\lambda}_K, \\ [\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}}]_I &= \int_S \Delta \tilde{p} \psi_I^m dS, \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^m N_y^m, \quad J = 1, \dots, N_x^m N_y^m. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

106 The mass and stiffness matrices $-\mathbf{M}$ and \mathbf{K} , respectively, are computed via Gauss-Legendre quadrature [45],
 107 whereas the vector of generalized aerodynamic forces $-\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}}$ is written in terms of the nodal displacements
 108 $-\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ as shown in the next section.

109 Finally, it must be pointed that we have obtained satisfactory results in this work by choosing $N_x^m =$
 110 $N_y^m = 20$.

3. Aerodynamic model

3.1. General unsteady equations

As with the elastic model, the three-dimensional aerodynamic flow past the plate is described by means of a linearized and small-perturbation theory [9, 10, 41, 46]. In this approximation, the plate and the wake are assumed to have no thickness and to be placed, respectively, at the domains $[0, L] \times [-H/2, H/2]$ and $[L, \infty) \times [-H/2, H/2]$ of the $x - y$ plane, independently of the kind of their small amplitude motion, with the x -axis parallel to the incident flow far from the plate, as indicated before (see Fig. 1). The flow is considered non-viscous and irrotational in the rest of the domain, and hence it can be described by means of a velocity potential ϕ that verifies the convected wave equation, i.e.,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 \phi = a_\infty^2 \nabla^2 \phi, \quad (10)$$

being a_∞ the upstream sound speed. The boundary conditions are those of non-penetration at the plate's surface,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial z_p}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial z_p}{\partial x}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq L, \quad -H/2 \leq y \leq H/2, \quad z = 0^+, \quad (11)$$

non-perturbed infinity,

$$\nabla \phi = 0, \quad x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \rightarrow \infty, \quad (12)$$

equilibrium of pressures at the wake –or generalized Kutta condition–,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} = 0, \quad x > L, \quad -H/2 \leq y \leq H/2, \quad z = 0^+, \quad (13)$$

and mass conservation through the wake

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}(x, y, 0^+) = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}(x, y, 0^-), \quad 0 \leq x \leq L, \quad -H/2 \leq y \leq H/2. \quad (14)$$

It is important to remark that the potential is antisymmetric with respect to the $x - y$ plane and that it presents a finite jump discontinuity across the region occupied by the plate and the wake.

The solution of (10)-(14) can be described [46, 47] by means of a distribution along the plate of singularities called *doublets*, and whose intensities equal the pressure jumps across the plate. In that case, equations (10), (12)-(14) are automatically fulfilled, whereas equation (11) determines the pressure jumps across the plate. In particular, if we make $\phi = \text{Re} [\tilde{\phi} \exp(j\omega t)]$ and $z_p = \text{Re} [\tilde{z}_p \exp(j\omega t)]$ and express $\tilde{\phi}$ in terms of the distribution of doublets, equation (11) reads as the so-called Possio equation [42]

$$j\omega \tilde{z}_p(x, y) + U_\infty \frac{\partial \tilde{z}_p}{\partial x}(x, y) = \int_S \Delta \tilde{p}(\xi, \eta) K(x - \xi, y - \eta) d\xi d\eta, \quad (15)$$

with K the kernel function. The latter is written as

$$K(x_0, y_0) = \frac{\exp(-jk \frac{2x_0}{L})}{\pi \rho_\infty U_\infty L^2} \left[\frac{M_\infty \exp(jkX)}{R \sqrt{X^2 + r^2}} + B(k, r, X) \right],$$

where $k := \omega L / (2U_\infty)$ is the so-called reduced frequency,

$$r := \frac{2|y_0|}{L}, \quad R := \sqrt{\left(\frac{2x_0}{L}\right)^2 + (1 - M_\infty^2)r^2}, \quad X := \frac{2x_0/L - M_\infty R}{1 - M_\infty^2},$$

and $B(k, r, X)$ is the complex-valued integral

$$B(k, r, X) := \int_{-\infty}^X \frac{\exp(jkv)}{(v^2 + r^2)^{3/2}} dv,$$

which is computed in the Mangler's sense by means of the series found in [42, 47].

It is worth remarking that the l.h.s. of (15) represents the vertical velocities of the flow at the plate [47].

137 *3.2. Numerical discretization*

138 In order to solve equation (15), we have implemented a doublet point method developed by Ueda and
 139 Dowell [42]. In their approach, the plate is divided into $N_x^a \times N_y^a$ rectangular and uniform panel segments
 140 –say *aerodynamic grid*–, which are numbered from from 1 to $N_x^a N_y^a$ following first the x direction, as shown
 141 in Fig. 2(a)¹. At each panel I , we define a doublet point (x_I^p, y_I^p) and an upwash point (x_I^w, y_I^w) –at which
 142 the pressure jumps and the flow vertical velocities are to be evaluated– at 1/4 and 3/4 of the mean chord,
 143 respectively, as depicted in Fig. 2(b). Then, and taking into account equation (2), the integral equation
 144 (15) is discretized as

$$\sum_{J=1}^{N_x^a N_y^a} \left[j\omega\psi_J(x_I^w, y_I^w) + U_\infty \frac{\partial\psi_J}{\partial x}(x_I^w, y_I^w) \right] \tilde{q}_J = \sum_{J=1}^{N_x^a N_y^a} \Delta\tilde{p}(x_J^p, y_J^p) S_J K(x_I^w - x_J^p, y_I^w - y_J^p), \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a,$$

145 with S_J the surface of the panel J . In matrix form, the latter equation reads

$$\mathbf{F}\tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}\tilde{\mathbf{p}}, \quad (16)$$

146 with

$$[\mathbf{F}]_{IJ} = j\omega\psi_J(x_I^w, y_I^w) + U_\infty \frac{\partial\psi_J}{\partial x}(x_I^w, y_I^w), \quad [\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}]_{IK} = S_K K(x_I^w - x_K^p, y_I^w - y_K^p), \quad [\tilde{\mathbf{p}}]_K = \Delta\tilde{p}(x_K^p, y_K^p),$$

$$I = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a, \quad J = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a, \quad K = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a. \quad (17)$$

Figure 2: (a) Scheme of the grid employed for the aerodynamic discretization. (b) Location of the doublet point (x_I^p, y_I^p) and the upwash point (x_I^w, y_I^w) on the i -th panel segment following the the 1/4 - 3/4 chord rule.

147 System (16) allows to obtain the pressure jumps at the plate from the values of the generalized coordi-
 148 nates. At the same time, the generalized aerodynamic forces can be computed from the values of the
 149 pressure jumps following relation (9), which can be discretized as

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}}]_I = \sum_{J=1}^{N_x^a N_y^a} \psi_I^m(x_J^p, y_J^p) \Delta\tilde{p}(x_J^p, y_J^p) S_J.$$

¹Note that the aerodynamic grid and the mechanical grid do not coincide.

150 In matrix form, the latter relation reads

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \mathbf{G}\tilde{\mathbf{p}}, \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^m N_y^m, \quad (18)$$

151 with

$$[\mathbf{G}]_{IJ} := \psi_I^m(x_J^p, y_J^p) S_J, \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^m N_y^m, \quad J = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a.$$

152 Combining equations (16) and (18), we arrive to the linear relation

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \Upsilon \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (19)$$

153 with

$$\Upsilon := \mathbf{G} (\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}})^{-1} \mathbf{F}. \quad (20)$$

154 We strongly emphasize that system (20) must be solved without explicitly inverting \mathbf{D}^{aero} , but by using an
155 appropriate method (e.g., LU decomposition).

156 It is also important to remark that, following [47], in this work we have employed an aerodynamic
157 discretization of $N_x^a = 80$ and $N_y^a = \lceil AR \cdot N_x^a \rceil$ –with $AR := H/L$ the aspect ratio– in order to achieve
158 convergence for the flutter speed and the flutter frequency.

159 3.3. Optimization of the doublet point method

160 \mathbf{D}^{aero} is a $N_x^a N_y^a \times N_x^a N_y^a$ dense matrix. Thus, when the number of aerodynamic panels is large, both the
161 direct evaluation of all its elements from (17) and the resolution of the system (20) become very expensive
162 –of $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^2)$ and $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^3)$ flops, respectively. To alleviate this drawback, we have considered the
163 following.

164 First, we must note from (17) that the value of $[\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}]_{IJ}$ does not depend separately on the coordinates
165 of the upwash point I and of the doublet point J , but on the relative position between them. Since the
166 mesh is rectangular and uniform, it follows that only $(2N_x^a + 1)(2N_y^a + 1)$ components of \mathbf{D}^{aero} from the
167 total of $(N_x^a N_y^a)^2$ are different. Thus, we can first evaluate those different components from equation (17)
168 –an expensive task *per component*– and then copy their values to the rest of the matrix components –an
169 insignificantly expensive task *per component*–. Note that the complexity of computing \mathbf{D}^{aero} with this
170 procedure is still $O(4N_x^a N_y^a) + O((N_x^a N_y^a)^2) \sim O((N_x^a N_y^a)^2)$, although now the average cost of computing
171 each element of the matrix is much smaller.

172 Second, we have applied a condensation technique –as suggested in [42]– to reduce the size of the system
173 (20). For this purpose, we have defined a *condensation grid* –similar to the mechanical one– formed by
174 $N_x^c \times N_y^c$ Chebyshev nodes distributed over the plate. Then, the pressure jumps over the plate have been
175 described by means of their values at the condensation grid nodes as

$$\Delta \tilde{p}(x, y) = \sum_{I=1}^{N_x^c N_y^c} \sqrt{\frac{(L_y/2)^2 - y^2}{x}} \psi_I^c(x, y) \Delta \tilde{p}(x_I^c, y_I^c), \quad (21)$$

176 with (x_I^c, y_I^c) the coordinates of the I -th node of the condensation grid and ψ_I^c the associated Lagrange
177 polynomial. Note that the approximation of Δp takes into account the singularities at the leading and
178 lateral edges. Now, we consider a matrix \mathbf{W} whose J -th column is the Lagrange polynomial ψ_J^c evaluated
179 at the upwash points, i.e.,

$$[\mathbf{W}]_{IJ} := \psi_J^c(x_I^w, y_I^w), \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a, \quad J = 1, \dots, N_x^c N_y^c,$$

180 project equation (16) onto the subspace spanned by the columns of \mathbf{W} and use (21) to obtain

$$(\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{F}) \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}} \mathbf{P}) \hat{\mathbf{p}}, \quad (22)$$

181 with

$$[\mathbf{P}]_{IJ} := \sqrt{\frac{(L_y/2)^2 - (y_I^p)^2}{x_I^p}} \psi_J^c(x_I^p, y_I^p), \quad [\hat{\mathbf{p}}]_J := \Delta \tilde{p}(x_J^c, y_J^c), \quad I = 1, \dots, N_x^a N_y^a, \quad J = 1, \dots, N_x^c N_y^c.$$

182 Taking into account that $\tilde{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{P}\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and combining (18) with (22), we arrive to

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \hat{\mathbf{Y}}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (23)$$

183 where

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} := (\mathbf{G}\mathbf{P}) (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}} \mathbf{P})^{-1} (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{F}). \quad (24)$$

184 Note that computing the matrix $\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}} \mathbf{P}$ in (24) requires $O((N_x^c N_y^c)(N_x^a N_y^a)^2 + (N_x^c N_y^c)^2 (N_x^a N_y^a))$ flops,
 185 whereas solving the system (24) requires $O((N_x^c N_y^c)^3)$. Recalling that the cost of the original system (20)
 186 is $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^3)$, it is clear that we can greatly improve the scheme's efficiency while keeping its accuracy
 187 if we choose N_x^c and N_y^c so that $N_x^c N_y^c \ll N_x^a N_y^a$ but, at the same time, (21) remains as a good approx-
 188 imation to the pressure jumps over the plate. In that case, the total cost of constructing and solving
 189 (24) drops to $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^2)$. In this work, we have obtained satisfactory results with $N_x^c = \min\{25, N_x^a\}$,
 190 $N_y^c = \min\{25, N_y^a\}$.

191 To illustrate how these two modifications affect to the computational cost, we have evaluated the matrix
 192 \mathbf{Y} with the original and with the optimized methods for $\rho_\infty = 1$, $U_\infty = 12$, $M_\infty = 0.5$, $k = 0.8$ and several
 193 values of AR . Then, we have compared the times spent on computing the matrix \mathbf{D}^{aero} and on solving the
 194 systems (20) and (24), as well as the total time needed for computing \mathbf{Y} . The experiments were performed
 195 in a ten-core Intel i9-7900X CPU 3.30 GHz machine with 32 GB of RAM. As can be seen in Table 1, when
 196 the number of aerodynamic panels is doubled, the cost of computing \mathbf{D}^{aero} is approximately multiplied
 197 by four in both methods, as expected, although the optimized method is about 20 times faster. It is also
 198 observed that the cost of solving system (20) in the original method increases significantly faster with the
 199 number of panels than that of system (24) in the optimized method². As a consequence, the total time
 200 spent on computing \mathbf{Y} is about 7 or 15 times faster –depending on the number of aerodynamic panels–
 201 for the case of the optimized method.

Table 1: Profiling times (in seconds) for the original and the optimized methods. $t_{\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}}$ denotes the time spent on computing \mathbf{D}^{aero} , t_{system} the time spent on solving (20) or (24), and $t_{\mathbf{Y}}$ the total time to compute \mathbf{Y} .

AR	$N_x^a \times N_y^a$	Original method			Optimized method		
		$t_{\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}}$	t_{system}	$t_{\mathbf{Y}}$	$t_{\mathbf{D}^{\text{aero}}}$	t_{system}	$t_{\mathbf{Y}}$
0.2	1280	0.6152	0.0932	0.7412	0.0250	0.0953	0.1219
0.4	2560	2.5902	0.3770	3.0334	0.1169	0.2006	0.3308
0.8	5120	10.0324	1.6360	11.8340	0.4766	0.4911	0.9910
1.6	10240	39.2411	9.4669	49.2255	1.7431	1.3164	3.1356

202 3.4. Validation of the aerodynamic model

203 In order to validate the aerodynamic model, we have considered the harmonic motion of a rigid plate –
 204 characterized by two shape functions: $\psi_1(x, y) = 1$ and $\psi_2(x, y) = -x$ – and computed the evolution of the lift
 205 and of the leading edge pitching moment (positive nose-up) coefficients along the time given some arbitrary
 206 initial conditions. Then, we have compared the results obtained with the optimized method proposed in the
 207 previous section with those of the original Ueda-Dowell method.

208 Fig. 3 shows the results for different values of the plate's aspect ratio and of the upstream Mach number.
 209 As can be seen, there is a good agreement between the optimized method and the original one. Indeed,
 210 the relative errors of the results are of the order of 10^{-5} with respect to those obtained with the original
 211 Ueda-Dowell method.

²Note that the cost of solving systems (20) and (24) do not behave strictly as $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^3)$ nor $O((N_x^a N_y^a)^2)$, respectively. This is due to the fact that, in reality, the costs of multiplying matrices and solving systems of dimension N are not strictly proportional to $O(N^3)$, as one would expect from theory, but depend also on the employed computation libraries and on the processor's architecture.

Figure 3: Evolution of the lift and of the leading edge pitching moment (positive nose-up) coefficients $-C_L$ and C_M , respectively— for different values of M_∞ and AR , obtained with both the original [42] and the optimized doublet point method.

212 4. Computation of the flutter point

213 If we couple the relation between the aerodynamic forces and the displacements of the plate (23) to its
214 equation of motion (8), we obtain that, at the flutter point,

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K} - \hat{\mathbf{Y}} & \mathbf{R}^T \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \\ \tilde{\lambda} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

215 which can be written in a shorter form as

$$\Theta \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0} \quad (26)$$

216 with

$$\Theta := \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K} - \hat{\mathbf{Y}} & \mathbf{R}^T \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{x} := \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \\ \tilde{\lambda} \end{bmatrix}.$$

217 For convenience, we will consider that the parameters of the plate (σ, D, L, H, ν) and the upstream density
218 and Mach number are fixed, so that Θ depends only on two unknowns: the flutter speed, U_f , and the flutter
219 frequency, ω_f .

220 A common approach [48] for finding a nontrivial solution of (26) consists on employing a quasi-Newton
221 method to solve the equivalent (complex) equation $\det(\Theta(U_f, \omega_f)) = 0$. However, in our case, the determi-
222 nant of Θ is typically that large that its computation leads to overflow problems. This inconvenience can be
223 overcome by the procedure described hereafter. Let $\mu_1(U_f, \omega_f), \dots, \mu_{N_\theta}(U_f, \omega_f)$ (with $|\mu_1| \leq \dots \leq |\mu_{N_\theta}|$)
224 be the $N_\theta := N_x^m N_y^m + 2N_y$ eigenvalues of $\Theta(U_f, \omega_f)$, and let $K_s > 0$ be a user-defined parameter. Then,
225 we define

$$\mu^*(U_f, \omega_f) := \prod_{i=1}^{N_\theta} [K_s \mu_i(U_f, \omega_f)] = \exp \left(N_\theta \ln K_s + \sum_{i=1}^{N_\theta} \ln \mu_i(U_f, \omega_f) \right). \quad (27)$$

As can be seen from the first equality in (27), μ^* is proportional to $\det(\Theta)$, although it is computed in a way that overflow can be avoided if K_s is adequately fine-tuned. The second equality in (27) represents a numerically more stable way to compute μ^* . For the moment, the function μ^* allows to numerically compute the flutter point in a stable way by solving the (complex) equation $\mu^* = 0$. However, we have found that we can obtain additional stability by reducing the influence of the largest eigenvalues in (27). This can be done by redefining μ^* as

$$\mu^*(U_f, \omega_f) := \prod_{i=1}^{N_\theta} \left[K_s \frac{\mu_i(U_f, \omega_f)}{|\mu_i(U_f, \omega_f)| + \delta_s} \right] = \exp \left(N_\theta \ln K_s + \sum_{i=1}^{N_\theta} \ln \frac{\mu_i(U_f, \omega_f)}{|\mu_i(U_f, \omega_f)| + \delta_s} \right), \quad (28)$$

with $\delta_s > 0$ a user-defined parameter (in this work, we have set $\delta_s = 0.5$). Note that equation (26) is equivalent to

$$\operatorname{Re}(\mu^*(U_f, \omega_f)) = \operatorname{Im}(\mu^*(U_f, \omega_f)) = 0, \quad (29)$$

since $\mu_1 = 0$ at the flutter point. Note as well that the modulus of the term in brackets in the first equality in (28) is approximately K_s for those (large) eigenvalues with $|\mu_i| \gg \delta_s$, and nearly $K_s |\mu_i| / \delta_s$ for those (small) eigenvalues with $|\mu_i| \ll \delta_s$. Thus, $\mu^*(U_f, \omega_f)$ remains bounded far away from its roots whereas, close to its roots, it behaves in a way similar to that of the product of those small eigenvalues, which in practice we have found to vary monotonously and smoothly w.r.t. the variables U_f and ω_f . The latter point is essential to make quasi-Newton solvers work in a stable and efficient manner when solving (29).

An important aspect that must be considered to solve (25) is that the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ gets ill-conditioned when the flutter reduced frequency, k_f , is greater than 6. Thus, if we employ an iterative solver for (29), it is convenient to ensure that $k_f < 6$ at each iteration. Likewise, the restrictions $U_f, \omega_f, k_f > 0$ should also be taken into account. To address this point, we have considered (U_f, ω_f, k_f) as the unknowns, added the equation

$$\omega_f L_x - 2U_f k_f = 0$$

to the system (29) and employed reflective techniques [49, 50] at each iteration.

Finally, if we are not interested in computing a single flutter point, but a whole continuation curve w.r.t. a certain parameter –e.g. ρ_∞ or H –, it may be necessary to update K_s at each point of the curve. For this purpose, we numerically compute the derivatives of $\operatorname{Re}(\mu^*)$ and $\operatorname{Im}(\mu^*)$ w.r.t. U_f and ω_f at the (given) last computed point of the curve, and update K_s through the formula

$$K_s \leftarrow K_s \left[\sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \operatorname{Re}(\mu^*)}{\partial U_f} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \operatorname{Im}(\mu^*)}{\partial U_f} \right)^2} \right]^{-\frac{1}{N_\theta}}.$$

Note that, if μ^* were recomputed with the new K_s , the term between brackets –which is a kind of average of those derivatives– would be 1. Thus, by this approach, we force μ^* to take moderate derivatives at the vicinities of the points of the curve.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Flutter curves

Fig. 4 shows the results obtained with the present method for the dependence of the dimensionless flutter speed U_f^* and of the dimensionless flutter frequency ω_f^* with the dimensionless density ρ^* , defined as

$$U_f^* = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} L U_f, \quad \omega_f^* = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} L^2 \omega_f, \quad \rho^* = \frac{\rho_\infty L}{\sigma},$$

for different upstream Mach numbers and plate aspect ratios, for a plate with Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.33$ –which is the typical value for the case of aluminium materials–. It can be seen that, for low Mach numbers, the flutter speed presents two peaks at certain values of ρ^* , whereas the flutter frequency presents two jumps at

those values. These peaks appear at $\rho^* \simeq 3$ and $\rho^* \simeq 10$ for $AR = 0.2$ and move leftwards when the aspect ratio increases. As the Mach number increases, those peaks and jumps become smoother. In addition, the number of peaks in the represented interval of ρ^* increases with the aspect ratio for high values of the Mach number.

In addition, Fig. 5 shows the evolution of the dimensionless flutter speed and frequency with the aspect ratio for different Mach numbers and a fixed value $\rho^* = 0.6$. As can be seen, there is a jump both in the flutter speed and frequency for $AR \simeq 1$, which in this case seems to be more noticeable for values of higher Mach numbers, unlike for the cases shown in Fig. 4. Excepting those jumps, the flutter speed diminishes with AR and increases with M_∞ , whereas the flutter frequency does not follow a general rule: it can increase or decrease depending on M_∞ and AR . Note that the two-dimensional limits obtained by Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28] have been included in the figure as a way to check the quality of our results for large values of AR .

On the other hand, Fig. 6 compares some of the results commented above with those obtained for $\nu = 0.26$, which is typical of steel materials, so that we can analyze the dependence of the solution on the Poisson's ratio. As can be seen, the latter has a very little impact both on the flutter speed and on the flutter frequency.

As a way to check the results, Figs. 7 and 8 compare, respectively, the flutter curves $U_f^* - \rho^*$ and $U_f^* - AR$ computed with our method for $M_\infty = 0.01$ with those of other authors such as Kornecki et al. [13], Eloy et al. [17], Souilliez et al. [51], Huang [7], Yamaguchi et al. [29], and Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28]. As can be seen, the agreement of the results for 3D flows is very good, as well as their convergence to the 2D case for large values of AR .

The flutter modes obtained with the present method for different combinations of the Mach number and the dimensionless density are plotted in Figs. 9 (for $AR = 0.2$), 10 (for $AR = 1$) and 11 (for $AR = 2$). As can be seen, the oscillations along the y -axis become more noticeable as the aspect ratio increases, which is expectable since the latter provides more ability for the plate to perform vertical displacements. On the other hand, the compressibility tends to increase the size of the neck of the flutter modes and, in the case of large aspect ratios, to increase the oscillations along the y -axis. Finally, it is observed that the size of the neck of the flutter modes decrease when the dimensionless density increases.

In addition, Fig. 12 compares the flutter modes computed for $AR = 1$ and incompressible flow with those obtained experimentally by Eloy et al. [17] for 3D plates, and numerically by Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28] for 2D plates, showing reasonable agreement. The main discrepancy w.r.t. the experimental results is found for the size of the neck, but this is due to the fact that the displacements are not really small, and thus a nonlinear theory should be considered to get more accuracy [27]. In any case, Fig. 12 shows that the method presented here can provide reliable results.

We remark that is important to consider an appropriate number of shape functions along the y -axis in order to obtain a realistic approximation to the deformation of the plate, especially for high values of the aspect ratio –see, e.g., Figs. 9 to 11–.

5.2. Dependence of the solution on the mechanical grid

As said in section 2, we have employed $N_x^m = N_y^m = 20$ for the mechanical grid discretization. In order to check if this choice is appropriate, we have performed a convergence analysis of the flutter solution w.r.t. the parameters N_x^m and N_y^m –assuming $N_x^m = N_y^m$ – for different values of the aspect ratio, the Mach number and the dimensionless density. In effect, Fig. 13 shows that in all cases both the flutter velocity and the flutter frequency vary less than a 10^{-3} relative when $N_x^m = N_y^m$ change from 15 to 20. Therefore, taking $N_x^m = N_y^m = 20$ can be considered sufficient to capture the flutter solution.

Figure 4: Dimensionless flutter speed and frequency as a function of the dimensionless density for various Mach numbers and aspect ratios.

Figure 5: Dimensionless flutter speed and frequency as a function of the aspect ratio for various Mach numbers and a fixed value of the dimensionless density ($\rho^* = 0.6$). The two-dimensional limits computed by Colera and Pérez-Saborid in [28] are shown in dashed lines to check the convergence of our model for high values of AR .

Figure 6: Dimensionless flutter speed and frequency as a function of the dimensionless density for various Mach numbers and two values of the Poisson's ratio ($\nu = 0.33$ is represented with a solid line, and $\nu = 0.26$ with a dashed one).

Figure 7: Comparison of the dimensionless flutter speed for $AR = 0.2$ and $AR = 1$ computed with the present method with that obtained numerically by Eloy et al. [16], Kornecki et al. [13], and Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28], and experimentally by Souilliez et al. [51], Huang [7] and Yamaguchi et al. [29].

Figure 8: Comparison of the dimensionless flutter speed computed with the present method for $\rho^* = 0.6$ and for different aspect ratios with that obtained numerically by Eloy et al. [17], Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28] and Kornecki et al. [13], and experimentally by Eloy et al. [17].

Figure 9: Flutter modes for a plate of aspect ratio $AR = 0.2$ and different values of the Mach number and of the dimensionless density.

Figure 10: Flutter modes for a plate of aspect ratio $AR = 1$ and different values of the Mach number and of the dimensionless density.

Figure 11: Flutter modes for a plate of aspect ratio $AR = 2$ and different values of the Mach number and of the dimensionless density.

Figure 12: Comparison between the experimental results obtained by Eloy et al. [17] (upper figures), those numerically computed by Colera and Pérez-Saborid [28] (central figures) and those obtained with the present method (bottom figures). In the latter, the outer profile ($y = H/2$) is represented in blue, whereas the central one ($y = 0$) is represented in orange.

Figure 13: Convergence of U_f^* and ω_f^* with the number of Chebyshev nodes N_x^m and N_y^m , assuming $N_x^m = N_y^m$. $(\cdot)_{\text{sol}}$ denotes the value corresponding to $N_x^m = N_y^m = 20$.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we perform a numerical analysis of the flutter instability of a three-dimensional, cantilevered, flexible plate subject to a compressible flow, as an extension of the work done in [28] for the two-dimensional case. For this purpose, we have discretized the dynamic equations of the plate by means of the virtual work principle and computed the generalized (linear) aerodynamic forces with a modification of the Ueda-Dowell method [42, 47]. Then, the instability points are computed by obtaining the eigenvalues of a matrix whose size is only determined by the number of structural degrees of freedom.

Despite the method has been applied only to the case of a cantilevered plate in this work, it has been implemented in such a way that it is also valid for other boundary conditions and other shapes of the plate, including those with tapering and sweeping. In general, the model is valid for any three-dimensional, flexible plate with a linear equation of motion. The obtained results are in good agreement with other numerical and experimental ones found in the literature [7, 13, 17, 28, 29, 51]. **To the best of our knowledge, this is the first computational investigation performed in the literature about the effects of compressibility on the flutter of a plate cantilevered at the leading edge in a three dimensional, inviscid, subsonic flow.**

The results show that the effect of the air compressibility is to reduce the intensity of the peaks and jumps that both the flutter speed and the flutter frequency experience when the dimensionless density increases, being considerably smoother when the Mach number reaches $M_\infty = 0.85$ –assuming that no transonic behavior appears in this range–. Another interesting conclusion is that, when the plate aspect ratio increases, those peaks and jumps appear for lower values of the dimensionless density. In addition, for a fixed value of the latter, both the evolution of the flutter speed and frequency with respect to the aspect ratio present a jump that seems to be more noticeable for higher values of Mach number. Excepting those jumps, the flutter speed diminishes with the aspect ratio and increases with the Mach number, whereas the flutter frequency does not follow a general rule. On the other hand, we have computed the corresponding curves for different Poisson’s ratios $-\nu = 0.33$ and $\nu = 0.26$, corresponding to the case of aluminium and steel materials respectively–, concluding that this parameter hardly affects both the flutter speed and the flutter frequency.

The effect of the air compressibility and the plate aspect ratio is also notable on the flutter modes. The former tends to affect mainly the shape of the oscillations, whereas the latter provokes the appearance of waves along the y -direction when it increases.

We hope that our work may be useful for those researchers in the field of aeroelasticity interested in studying the flutter instability of a **plate cantilevered at the leading edge subject to a three-dimensional subsonic flow**, providing some insight about the influence of different parameters, such as the compressibility, the aspect ratio and the material properties. We also expect that the numerical method developed here be useful for future studies that consider different boundary conditions –e.g., **inverted flags [52], yawed flows [53], sides attached to springs [38]**– and/or different shapes of the plate. Other tasks could be addressed in the future, **such as the inclusion of structural nonlinearities [54], the implementation of a higher-order aerodynamic scheme, and the extension of the analysis to supersonic flow.**

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